

46th - 46ième

**Annual Meeting - Réunion Annuelle
2014**

**Montréal, Québec
Canada**

September 18-20 Septembre

**CANADIAN ASSOCIATION of
PAEDIATRIC SURGEONS
ASSOCIATION CANADIENNE de
CHIRURGIE PÉDIATRIQUE**

**46th Annual Meeting
46 ième Réunion Annuelle**

September 18-20 Septembre 2014
Montréal Marriott Château Champlain
Montréal, Québec
CANADA

SCIENTIFIC AND SOCIAL PROGRAM PROGRAMME SCIENTIFIQUE ET SOCIAL

**Wednesday, September 17, 2014
Mercredi, 17 Septembre 2014**

Start Time	End Time	Function	Room
08:00	11:45	CAPS Executive Meeting	Etude Champlain
12 :00	17:00	CAPS Council Meeting	Etude Champlain
17:00	19:00	CAPSNet Meeting	Etude Champlain

**Thursday, September 18, 2014
Jeudi, 18 Septembre 2014**

Start Time	End Time	Function	Room
06:30	10:00	Publication Committee Meeting	Etude Champlain
08:00	16:00	Speaker Ready Room	Salon 402
07:00	16:00	Registration	Ballroom Foyer
12:00	16:30	Scientific Sessions	Ballroom
18:30	23:00	Welcome Reception and Buffet	Le Caf 'Conc'

**Friday, September 19, 2014
Vendredi, 19 Septembre 2014**

Start Time	End Time	Function	Room
06:30	08:00	RCPSC Specialty Committee Meeting	Etude Champlain
06:30	08:00	Global Partnership Meeting	TBA
07:00	16:00	Registration	Ballroom Foyer
07:00	16 :30	Poster Display	Viger AB & C
07:00	08:00	Continental Breakfast	Viger AB & C
07:00	16:30	Exhibits	Viger AB & C
07:00	16:30	Speaker Ready Room	Salon 402
08:00	16:30	Scientific Sessions	Ballroom
		All Breaks and Lunch	Viger AB & C

Saturday, September 20, 2014
Samedi, 20 Septembre 2014

Start Time	End Time	Function	Room
06:30	07 :00	CAPS Annual Business Breakfast Buffet	Maisonneuve A
07:00	09 :15	CAPS Annual General Meeting	Maisonneuve BC
08 :00	09:30	Continental Breakfast for Non-Members	Viger AB & C
08:00	14:00	Poster Display	Viger AB & C
08:00	15:00	Exhibits	Viger AB & C
08:00	14:00	Speaker Ready Room	Salon 402
09 :30	12:00	Registration	Ballroom Foyer
09:30	14:10	Scientific Sessions	Ballroom
18:30	24:00	CAPS Presidential Reception and Banquet	Ballroom Foyer / Ballroom

10th Annual Meeting September 18, 2014
CHU Ste. Justine, Montreal
Room-Marcelle Lacoste, 9th Floor

7:00-7:45 am CaPSNIG business meeting-*members only*
Breakfast will be served

7:45 – 8:00 am Welcome & Introductions
CAPS President-Dr. Jack Langer
Monping Chiang & Kimberly Colapinto – Chair CaPSNIG

8:00 – 9:00 am Intestinal Atresia's (Dr. Pavan Brahmamdam)

9:00 - 9:30 am Coffee Break

9:30 - 10:15 am Is Another's Breast still the Best? The experience of Using Donor Breast Milk in Surgical Infants (Hazel Pleasants)

10:15 - 10:30 am Promoting Safe Administration of Expressed Breast Milk: Systematic Exploration of Errors in EBM Administration and Strategies for Prevention (Maria Manalo)

10:30 - 10:50 pm Case Study for the implementation of a protocol for managing GT dislodgement (Cindy Holland)

10:50 - 11:50 pm Lunch-*open discussion for interesting cases*

11:50- 12:50 pm 1. Doing Research. Ethics, Quality & Reality met in Pediatric Clinical Research
(*Eveline Lapidus-Krol*)

2. SHiKT: Integrated knowledge translation used to identify confidence in management of challenges faced by caregivers of Hirschsprung's Disease (*Kendall Hobbs-Murison*)

3. Family Health Literacy Levels and Patient In-Briefs: How Pediatric Surgery Nurse Practitioners can Communicate More Effectively in a Clinic Setting (*Julia Pond*)

4. Pregnancy urinary screening policy development and implementation in CHU Sainte-Justine (*Stephanie Duval*)

12:50 - 1:00 pm Closing remarks - **CAPS conference**

This meeting was made possible by the generous donation of CAPS. Please thank your surgeons!

THURSDAY, SEPTEMBER 18

12:00 - 12:15	President's Welcome	Jacob Langer
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		Scientific Session # 1 Oral Presentations Moderators: Helene Flageole & Corey Iqbal	
12:15 - 13:39			
1	O R	12:15 – 12:22	<p>Fundoplication versus percutaneous gastrojejunostomy for gastroesophageal reflux in children with neurologic impairment: A systematic review and meta-analysis Michael H Livingston ^{1,5,6}; Anna C Shawyer ^{1,2}; Peter L Rosenbaum ^{3,4}; Sarah A Jones ^{6,7}; J Mark Walton ^{1,2}</p> <p>¹ McMaster Pediatric Surgery Research Collaborative, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ² Division of Pediatric Surgery, McMaster Children's Hospital, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ³ CanChild Centre for Childhood Disability Research, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ⁴ Department of Pediatrics, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ⁵ Clinician Investigator Program, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ⁶ Division of General Surgery, Western University, London, Ontario, Canada ⁷ Division of Pediatric Surgery, Western University, London, Ontario, Canada</p>
2	O	12:27 – 12:34	<p>Thoracoscopic sympathectomies for primary palmar hyperhidrosis in children and adolescents Sabine Vasseur Maurer; Anthony De Buys Roessingh; Olivier Reinberg Dept. of Pediatric Surgery, University Hospital of Lausanne (CHUV), Lausanne, Switzerland</p>
3	O	12:39 – 12:46	<p>Treatment of esophageal achalasia in children: Today and tomorrow Caldaro T ¹; Familiari P ²; Romeo E ¹; Gigante G ²; Marchese M ²; Contini AC ¹; Federici Di Abriola G ¹; Cucchiara S ³; De Angelis P ¹; Torroni F ¹; Dall'oglio L ¹; Costamagna G ²</p> <p>¹ Digestive Surgery And Endoscopy Unit, Bambino Gesù Children's Hospital, Rome, Italy ² Digestive Surgical Endoscopy Unit, Catholic University, Rome, Italy ³ Department Of Pediatrics, Pediatric Gastroenterology and Liver Unit, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy</p>
4	O R	12:51 – 12:58	<p>Health-related quality of life in neonates and infants: A conceptual framework based on focus groups and interviews Carol Oliveira ^{1,2,3,4}; Nicole T. de Silva ¹; Wendy Ungar ^{3,4}; Ahmed Bayoumi ⁴; Yaron Avitzur ^{1,5}; Jeffrey Hoch ⁴; Julia Maxwell ¹; Paul W. Wales ^{1,2,3,4}</p> <p>¹ Group for Improvement of Intestinal Function and Treatment Program (GIFT), Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ² Division of General and Thoracic Surgery, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ³ Child Health Evaluative Sciences (CHES) Program, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ⁴ Institute of Health Policy, Management and Evaluation (IHPME), University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ⁵ Division of Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada</p>

5	O R	13:03 – 13:10	<p>The development of a competency based "Boot Camp" curriculum for pediatric surgery residents Christopher Blackmore ¹; Jocelyn Lockyer ²; Elizabeth Oddone Paolucci ²; Steve Lopushinsky ³ ¹ Department of Surgery, University of Calgary, Calgary, Alberta, Canada ² Department of Community Health Sciences, University of Calgary, Calgary, Alberta, Canada ³ Department of Surgery, Division of Pediatric Surgery, University of Calgary, Calgary, Alberta, Canada</p>
6	O	13:15 – 13:22	<p>Post-operative impact of nasogastric tubes on length of stay in infants with pyloric stenosis (POINTS): A randomized controlled trial Flageole Helene ^{1,2}; Pemberton Julia ¹ ¹ McMaster Pediatric Surgery Research Collaborative, Department of Surgery, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ² McMaster Children's Hospital, Hamilton Health Sciences, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada</p>
7	O R	13:27 – 13:34	<p>Granular cell tumor in children Hanna Alemayehu ¹; Stephanie F. Polites ²; Alexander Kats ³; Michael B. Ishitani ²; Christopher R. Moir ²; Corey W. Iqbal ¹ ¹ Department of Surgery, The Children's Mercy Hospital, Kansas City, Missouri, USA ² Department of Pediatric Surgery, Mayo Clinic, Rochester, Minnesota, USA ³ Department of Pathology, The Children's Mercy Hospital, Kansas City, Missouri, USA</p>

13:39 - 14:15	Coffee Break
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14:15 - 14:30	Historical note - Frank Guttman
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		Scientific Session # 2	
		Oral Presentations	
14:30 - 15:49		Moderators: Kathryn Bass & Melanie Morris	
8	O	14:30 – 14:37	<p>A comparison of surgical outcomes between in-hours and after-hours tracheoesophageal fistula repairs Anthony Yeung ¹, Sonia A. Butterworth ² ¹ University of British Columbia, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada ² Division Of Pediatric Surgery, BC Children's Hospital, Vancouver, BC, Canada</p>
9	O	14:42 – 14:49	<p>Impact of host factors in predicting abdominal injuries from motor vehicle crashes (MVC) in children: The importance of analytical morphomics Zhang Peng; Lu Wang; Sven Holcombe; Carla Kohdya-Inglis; Stewart Wang; Peter Ehrlich University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA</p>
10	O R	14:54 – 15:01	<p>Morphometric analysis of abdominal organs and ribcage: Implication for risk of solid organ injuries in children Calista Harbaugh; Ryan Tsuchida; Maksim Shlykov; Sven Holcombe; Jake Hirschl; Stewart Wang; Peter Ehrlich International Center for Automotive Medicine, University of Michigan, Department of Surgery, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA</p>

11	O R	15:06 – 15:13	<p>Mortality among injured children treated at different trauma center types Chethan Sathya ^{1,2}; Aziz Alali ²; Paul Wales ³; Damon Scales ⁴; Paul Karanicolas ^{1,4,5}; Randell Burd ⁶; Michael Nance ⁸; Avery Nathens ^{1,2,4,5,7}</p> <p>¹ Division of General Surgery, Department of Surgery, University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ² Institute of Health Policy, Management, and Evaluation, University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ³ Division of General and Thoracic Surgery, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ⁴ Sunnybrook Research Institute, Sunnybrook Health Sciences Centre, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ⁵ Division of General Surgery, Department of Surgery, Sunnybrook Health Sciences Centre, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ⁶ Division of General Surgery, Children's Hospital of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA ⁷ Li Ka Shing Knowledge Institute, St. Michael's Hospital, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ⁸ Children's Hospital of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA</p>
12	O	15:18 – 15:25	<p>Adolescent weight loss- medical vs surgical treatment Christine Finck; Elizabeth Estrada; Melissa Santos; Diane Lombardi; Meghna Misra; Shefali Thaker Connecticut Children's Medical Center, Hartford, Connecticut, USA</p>
13	O R	15:30 – 15:37	<p>The seal technique: Routine technical modification is mandatory in order to prevent high recurrence rate Caroline Lemoine; Nelson Piché; Michel Lallier Pediatric General Surgery, CHU Sainte-Justine, Université de Montréal, Montréal, Québec, Canada</p>
14	T R	15:42 – 15:46	<p>Combined approach in the management of refractory chylous ascites in paediatric oncology patients Alkudayri A, Habib Z, Koussayer S Department of Surgery, King Faisal Hospital & Research Center, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia</p>

15:49 - 16:10		CAPSNet update – Erik Skarsgard
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18:30 - 23:00	Welcome Reception	
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FRIDAY, SEPTEMBER 19

08:00 - 09:24		Scientific Session # 3 Oral Presentations Moderators: Priscilla Chiu & BJ Hancock	
15	O R	08:00 – 08:07	Gastroschisis communities in Canada: A population-based analysis of community and personal risk factors Farhana Shariff ¹ ; Erik Skarsgard ² ; Laura Arbor ³ ; Kate Bassil ⁴ ; Mary Brindle ⁵ ¹ Department of General Surgery, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, BC, Canada ² Division of Pediatric General Surgery, Department of Surgery, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada ³ Department of Medical Genetics, University of British Columbia; Division of Medical Sciences, University of Victoria, Victoria, British Columbia, Canada ⁴ Dalla Lana School of Public Health, University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ⁵ Division of Pediatric General Surgery, Department of Surgery, University of Calgary, Calgary, Alberta, Canada
16	O R	08:12 – 08:19	The correlation between time spent in utero and bowel matting in newborns with gastroschisis Fouad Youssef; Jean-Martin Laberge; Robert Baird Division of Pediatric General and Thoracic Surgery, Montreal Children's Hospital, Montreal, Quebec, Canada
17	O R	08:24 – 08:31	Pacemaker cell status in gastroschisis Elke Zani-Ruttenstock, Anu Paul, Augusto Zani, Salvador Diaz-Cano, Niyi Ade-Ajayi King's College Hospital NHS Foundation Trust, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia
18	O R	08:36 – 08:43	Altered expression of BMP target genes involved in epithelial-mesenchymal transition suggests a pathogenic mechanism for esophageal atresia/tracheo-esophageal fistula in the adriamycin mouse model Danielle Mc Laughlin ^{1,2,3} ; Paula Murphy ² ; Prem Puri ^{1,4} ¹ National Children's Research Centre, Our Lady's Children's Hospital, Crumlin, Ireland ² School of Natural Sciences, Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland ³ Children's University Hospital, Dublin, Ireland ⁴ Conway Institute of Biomolecular and Biomedical Research, University College, Dublin, Ireland
19	O R	08:48 – 08:55	Mucous fistula refeeding in neonates with enterostomies Candace A. Haddock ¹ , Jennifer D. Stanger ¹ , Susan G. Albersheim ² , Linda M. Casey ³ Sonia A. Butterworth ¹ ¹ Division of Pediatric Surgery, Department of Surgery, British Columbia Children's Hospital, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada ² Division of Neonatology, Department of Pediatrics, British Columbia Children's Hospital, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada ³ Division of Gastroenterology, Hepatology & Nutrition, Department of Pediatrics, British Columbia Children's Hospital, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada
20	O R	09:00 – 09:07	Glucagon-like peptide 2 therapy induces changes in morphology, histology, mrna expression and barrier function consistent with intestinal adaptation in a piglet model of neonatal short bowel syndrome David W. Lim ¹ ; Justine M. Turner ² ; Patricia L. Brubaker ³ ; Donna F. Vine ⁴ ; Faye Borthwick ⁴ ; Patrick N. Nation ⁵ ; Pamela Wizzard ² ; David L. Sigalet ⁶ ; David L. Bigam ¹ ; Paul W. Wales ⁷ ¹ Department of Surgery, University of Alberta, Edmonton, Alberta, Canada ² Department of Pediatrics, University of Alberta, Edmonton, Alberta, Canada ³ Department of Physiology, University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ⁴ Department of Agricultural, Food & Nutritional Science, University of Alberta, Edmonton, Alberta, Canada ⁵ Department of Laboratory Medicine & Pathology, University of Alberta, Edmonton, Alberta, Canada ⁶ Department of Surgery, University of Calgary, Calgary, Alberta, Canada

			⁷ Department of Surgery, University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada
21	OR	09:12 – 09:19	<p>Supplemental oxygen decreases severity and prolongs survival in a premature piglet model of spontaneous necrotizing enterocolitis</p> <p><u>Fariha Sheikh</u> ¹; Irving J. Zamora ¹; Adesola C. Akinkuotu ¹; Barbara Stoll ²; Ling Yu ¹; Douglas G. Burrin ²; Oluyinka O. Olutoye ¹</p> <p>¹ Division of Pediatric Surgery, Michael E. DeBakey Department of Surgery, Baylor College of Medicine, Texas Children's Hospital, Houston, Texas, USA</p> <p>² Department of Pediatrics, Baylor College of Medicine, USDA/ARS Children's Nutrition Research Center, Houston, Texas, USA</p>

09:24 - 09:45		CaPSNIG 10th Anniversary Presentation
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09:45 - 10:15		Coffee Break and Poster Viewing
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10:15 - 10:30		CAPS' Travelling Fellowship Recipient – Alana Beres
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		Scientific Session # 4	
		Poster Podium Presentations	
		Moderators: Annie Fecteau & Danny Little	
10:30 - 11:30			
22	P R	10:30	<p>Predictors of recurrence following repair of neonatal congenital diaphragmatic hernia</p> <p><u>Fariha Sheikh</u> ^{1,2}; Irving Zamora ^{1,2}; Raheel Ali ^{1,2}; Adesola Akinkuotu ^{1,2}; Tim C. Lee ^{1,2}; Oluyinka Olutoye ^{1,2,3,4}; Darrell Cass ^{1,2,3,4}</p> <p>¹ Texas Children's Fetal Center, Houston, Texas, USA</p> <p>² Baylor College of Medicine, Michael E. DeBakey Department of Surgery, Houston, Texas, USA</p> <p>³ Baylor College of Medicine, Department of Pediatrics, Houston, Texas, USA</p> <p>⁴ Baylor College of Medicine, Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Houston, Texas, USA</p>
23	P	10:34	<p>Repair of congenital diaphragmatic hernia under high frequency oscillatory ventilation and inhaled nitric oxide: An opportunity for earlier repair while minimizing lung injury</p> <p>Ayman Al-Jazaeri</p> <p>King Saud University, College of Medicine, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia</p>
24	P R	10:38	<p>Clinical characteristics and outcomes of patients with right congenital diaphragmatic hernia: A population-based study</p> <p>Catherine K Beaumier ¹; Alana L Beres ²; Pramod Puligandla ²; Erik Skarsgard ¹</p> <p>¹ BC Children's Hospital, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada</p> <p>² Montreal Children's Hospital, Montreal, Quebec, Canada</p>
25	P R	10:42	<p>Persistent hypercarbia after resuscitation is associated with increased mortality in congenital diaphragm hernia patients</p> <p>Paulette I. Abbas ^{1,2}; Darrell L. Cass ^{1,2,3}; Oluyinka O. Olutoye ^{1,2,3}; Irving J. Zamora ^{1,2}; Stephen E. Welty ^{1,3}; Timothy C. Lee ^{1,2}</p> <p>¹ Texas Children's Fetal Center, Houston, Texas, USA</p> <p>² Michael E. DeBakey Department of Surgery, Houston, Texas, USA</p> <p>³ Department of Pediatrics, Baylor College of Medicine, Houston, Texas, USA</p>
26	P R	10:46	<p>The RNA profile of nitrofen-induced hypoplastic lungs in congenital diaphragmatic hernia</p> <p>D. Johar ¹; T. Mahood ¹; W. Xu ²; R. Keijzer ^{1,3}</p> <p>¹ Manitoba Institute of Child Health, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada</p> <p>² Manitoba Institute of Cell Biology, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada</p> <p>³ Departments of Surgery and Physiology, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Manitoba,</p>

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27	P R	10:50	<p>The management of severe gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) in congenital diaphragmatic hernia (CDH) patients: A CAPSNeT Review of current practices <u>Taylor Petropoulos</u> ¹; Mary Brindle ²; Priscilla Chiu ¹; Eveline Lapidus-Krol ¹ ¹Division of Pediatric General and Thoracic Surgery, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ²Division of Pediatric Surgery, Alberta Children's Hospital, Calgary, Alberta, Canada</p>
28	P R	10:54	<p>The need for fundoplication following repair of esophageal atresia with or without tracheoesophageal fistula <u>Martin, KL</u>; Bass, J ; Nasr, A Division of General Surgery, Children's Hospital of Eastern Ontario, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada</p>
29	P R	10:58	<p>Feasibility and safety of sham feeding in long gap esophageal atresia Caroline Lemoine ¹; Christophe Faure ²; Andréanne Villeneuve ³; Keith Barrington ³; Claire Desrosiers ¹; Lise Thiboutot ¹; Ann Aspirot ¹ ¹Pediatric General Surgery, CHU Sainte-Justine, Université de Montréal, Montréal, Québec, Canada ²Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition, CHU Sainte-Justine, Université de Montréal, Montréal, Québec, Canada ³Neonatal and Perinatal Medicine, CHU Sainte-Justine, Université de Montréal, Montréal, Québec, Canada.</p>
30	P R	11:02	<p>Insurance status, race and gastroschisis in the United States <u>Benjamin Turner</u>; Carlos Sanchez-Glanville; Mary Brindle University of Calgary, Calgary, Alberta, Canada</p>
31	P R	11:06	<p>Post-ECMO chest tube placement: A propensity score-matched survival analysis Jun Tashiro ¹; Eduardo A. Perez ¹; David Lasko ²; Juan E. Sola ¹ ¹Division of Pediatric Surgery, DeWitt-Daughtry Family Department of Surgery, Leonard M. Miller School of Medicine, University of Miami, Miami, Florida, USA ²South Florida Pediatric Surgeons P.A., Plantation, Florida, USA</p>
32	P R	11:10	<p>Enteral Omega-3 lipids to control intestinal haemorrhage after serial transverse enteroplasty: A N-of-1 trial <u>Carol Oliveira</u> ^{1,2}; Nicole T. de Silva ^{1,2}; Paul W. Wales ^{1,2} ¹Group for Improvement of Intestinal Function and Treatment Program (GIFT), Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ²Division of General and Thoracic Surgery, The Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada</p>
33	P R	11:14	<p>Major thrombotic complications associated with lower extremity PICCs in surgical neonates Phyllis Kisa ¹; Joseph Ting ²; Allison Callejas ²; Horacio Osioviich ²; Sonia Butterworth ¹ ¹Division of Pediatric Surgery, University of British Columbia, British Columbia Children's Hospital, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada ²Division of Neonatology, University of British Columbia, British Columbia Children's Hospital, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada</p>
34	P R	11:18	<p>Systematic review and meta-analysis of surgical versus catheter-based treatment of the pediatric patent ductus arteriosus <u>Jennifer Lam</u> ; Steven Lopushinsky ; Irene Ma; Frank Dicke ; Mary Brindle University of Calgary, Calgary, Alberta, Canada</p>
35	P R	11:22	<p>Patient characteristics are not associated with failure of antibiotic-based line salvage <u>Christopher A. Guidry</u> ¹; David A. Cohen ¹; Robin T. Petroze ¹; Matthew L. Stone ¹; Bartholomew J. Kane ²; Eugene D. McGahren ²; Bradley M. Rodgers ²; Robert G. Sawyer ³; Sara K. Rasmussen ² ¹Department of Surgery, University of Virginia Health System, Charlottesville, Virginia, USA ²Division of Pediatric Surgery, Department of Surgery, University of Virginia Health System, Charlottesville, Virginia, USA ³Division of Acute Care and Trauma Surgery, Department of Surgery, University of Virginia</p>

			Health System, Charlottesville, Virginia, USA
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11:30 - 12:00	CAPS' President's Talk – Jacob Langer		
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12:00 - 12:30	Lunch Break – Lunch boxes		
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12:30 - 13:00		2 minutes – 2 slides; Videos Moderators: Robert Baird & Nelson Piché	
36	C	12:30	A 13-year-old girl with metastatic melanoma of unknown primary Grant G. Miller ¹ ; Fergall J. Magee ² ¹ Department of Surgery, University of Saskatchewan, Saskatoon, Saskatchewan, Canada ² Department of Pathology, Saskatoon Health Region, Saskatoon, Saskatchewan, Canada
37	CR	12:33	Unusual microtrauma causing chylothorax managed with VATS Lisa Taylor VanHouwelingen ¹ ; Jorge Zequeira ¹ ; Cecily Bos ² ; Helene Flageole ¹ ; Brian H Cameron ¹ ¹ Division of Pediatric Surgery, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ² Michael G. DeGroot School of Medicine, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada

38	C R	12:36	Neuroendocrine tumour of the pancreas causing biliary obstruction in a 12 year-old girl: A case report and literature review Kimberly A Bertens ¹ ; Michael Livingston ¹ ; Douglas Quan ¹ ; Kenneth Leslie ¹ ; Andreana Butter ^{1,2} ¹ Division of General Surgery, London Health Sciences Centre, Western University, London, Ontario, Canada ² Division of Pediatric Surgery, Children's Hospital, Western University, London, Ontario, Canada
39	C R	12:39	Prune belly syndrome in a female newborn with absent perineal openings with only a patent urachus Azhar Farooqui ¹ ; Alaa M AlAqeel ² ; Zakaria Habib ³ ¹ College of Medicine, Alfaisal University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia ² College of Medicine, King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia ³ Department of Pediatric Surgery, King Faisal Specialist Hospital and Research Center, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia
40	C R	12:42	Management of late presenting disorders of sexual differentiation in Africa. Alana L. Beres ¹ ; Jacques Ebhele ² ; Edmond Ntaganda ² ; Ronald Sutherland ³ ; Erik N. Hansen ² ¹ Montreal Children's Hospital, McGill University Health Centre, Montreal, Quebec, Canada ² Bethany Kids of Kijabe Hospital, Kijabe, Kenya ³ Kapi'olani Medical Center, Honolulu, Hawaii, USA
41	C R	12:45	Nature is amazing: A case of spontaneous fistulization in a patient with long gap esophageal atresia Claudia Emami; Dominique Levesque; Jean-Martin Laberge; Sherif Emil Montreal Children's Hospital, McGill University Health Centre, Montreal, Quebec, Canada
42	C R	12:48	An unusual case of pancreatic mass Caroline Lemoine ¹ ; Mona Beaunoyer ¹ ; Christophe Faure ² ; Ann Aspirot ¹ ¹ Pediatric General Surgery Department, CHU Sainte-Justine, Université de Montréal, Montréal, Québec, Canada ² Gastroenterology, Hepatology, and Nutrition Department, CHU Sainte-Justine, Université de Montréal, Montréal, Québec, Canada
43	C	12:51	Surgical resection and buccal mucosa vaginoplasty for local control in botryoid rhabdomyosarcoma Rodrigo LP Romao ¹ ; James Pierce ¹ ; Samina Afzal ¹ ; Dafydd Davies ¹ ; Conrad V

			Fernandez ¹ ; Mark Bernstein ¹ ; Armando J Lorenzo ² ¹ IWK Health Centre, Dalhousie University, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada ² Hospital for Sick Children, University of Toronto, Toronto, Ontario, Canada
44	C R	12:54	Diffuse pulmonary lymphangiomatosis with extensive mediastinal involvement : A case report Hau D. Le; Pavan Brahmamdam; David E. Manson; Bairbre Connely; Joao Amaral; Glen Taylor; Priscilla Chiu Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada
45	C R	12:57	Pulmonary capillary hemangiomatosis in a neonate with congenital diaphragmatic hernia Adesola C. Akinkuotu ^{1,2} ; Fariha Sheikh ^{1,2} ; Darrell L. Cass ^{1,2,3,4} ; Timothy C. Lee ^{1,2} ; Stephen E. Welty ^{1,3} ; Oluyinka O. Olutoye ^{1,2,3,4} ¹ Texas Children's Fetal Center, Houston, Texas, USA ² Michael E. DeBakey Department of Surgery, Houston, Texas, USA ³ Departments of Pediatric, Texas Children's Fetal Center, Houston, Texas, USA ⁴ Obstetrics and Gynecology, Baylor College of Medicine, Houston, Texas, USA

13:00 -14:36		Scientific Session # 5 Oral Presentations Moderators: Siggie Ein & Richard Keijzer	
46	O R	13:00 – 13:07	Predictors of poor outcomes in prenatally diagnosed sacrococcygeal teratoma: A multi-institutional review Adesola C. Akinkuotu ^{1,2} ; Alan Coleman ³ ; Eveline Shue ⁴ ; Fariha Sheikh ^{1,2} ; Shinjiro Hirose ⁴ ; Foong-Yen Lim ³ ; Oluyinka O. Olutoye ^{1,2,5,6} ¹ Texas Children's Fetal Center, Houston, Texas, USA ² Michael E. DeBakey Department of Surgery, Baylor College of Medicine, Houston, Texas, USA ³ Department of Pediatric Surgery, Fetal Care Center, Cincinnati Children's Hospital Medical Center, Cincinnati, Ohio, USA ⁴ Department of Surgery, Division of Pediatric Surgery and Fetal Treatment Center, University of California, San Francisco, San Francisco, California, USA ⁵ Department of Pediatrics, Baylor College of Medicine, Houston, Texas, USA ⁶ Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Baylor College of Medicine, Houston, Texas, USA
47	O R	13:12 – 13:19	Prenatally diagnosed neck masses: Long-term outcomes and quality of life Fariha Sheikh ^{1,2,6} ; Adesola Akinkuotu ^{1,2,6} ; Oluyinka O. Olutoye ^{1,2,3,4,6} ; Sheena Pimpalwar, ^{4,6} ; Christopher Cassady ^{4,6} ; Caraciolo J. Fernandes ^{5,6} ; Rodrigo Ruano ^{3,6} ; Timothy C. Lee ^{1,2,6} ; Darrell L. Cass ^{1,2,3,4,6} ¹ Texas Children's Fetal Center, Houston, Texas, USA ² Department of Surgery, Texas Children's Fetal Center, Houston, Texas, USA ³ Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Texas Children's Fetal Center, Houston, Texas, USA ⁴ Department of Radiology, Texas Children's Fetal Center, Houston, Texas, USA ⁵ Department of Pediatrics, Texas Children's Fetal Center, Houston, Texas, USA ⁶ Baylor College of Medicine, Houston, Texas, USA
48	O	13:24 – 13:31	Long-term nutritional morbidity for congenital diaphragmatic hernia survivors: failure to thrive extends well into childhood and adolescence B. Haliburton ¹ ; M. Mouzaki ² ; M. Chiang ¹ ; A. Zweerink ³ ; V. Scaini ² ; M. Marcon ² ; T Moraes ³ ; P. Chiu ¹ ¹ Division of Pediatric Surgery, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ² Division of Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada

			³ Division of Respiratory Medicine, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada
49	O R	13:36 – 13:43	Increased pulmonary vascular expression of receptor for advanced glycation end products (Rage) in experimental congenital diaphragmatic hernia Alejandro D. Hofmann ¹ ; Florian Friedmacher ¹ ; Toshiaki Takahashi ¹ ; Jan-Hendrik Gosemann ¹ ; Prem Puri ^{1,2} ¹ National Children's Research Centre, Our Lady's Children's Hospital, Crumlin, Dublin, Ireland ² School of Medicine and Medical Science and Conway Institute of Biomedical Research, University College, Dublin, Ireland

50	O	13:48 – 13:55	Association between congenital diaphragmatic hernia and undescended testes Kenneth Azarow ¹ ; Robert Cusick ² ; Julia Wynn ³ ; Wendy Chung ³ ; Marc Arkovitz ³ ; George Mychaliska ⁴ ; Timothy Crombleholme ⁵ ; Dai Chung ⁶ ; Foong-Yen Lim ⁷ ; Douglas Potolka ⁸ ; Brad Warner ⁹ ; Gudrun Aspelund ¹⁰ ; Marc Arkovitz ¹¹ ¹ Oregon Health Sciences University, Portland, Oregon, USA ² University of Nebraska Medical Center, Omaha, Nebraska, USA ³ Columbia University, New York City, New York, USA ⁴ University of Michigan School of Medicine, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA ⁵ Children's Hospital Colorado and the University of Colorado School of Medicine, Denver, Colorado, USA ⁶ Vanderbilt Children's Hospital, Nashville, Tennessee, USA ⁷ Cincinnati Children's Hospital Medical Center, Cincinnati, Ohio, USA ⁸ University of Pittsburgh School of Medicine, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA ⁹ Washington University School of Medicine, St. Louis, Missouri, USA ¹⁰ Columbia University, College of Physicians & Surgeons, New York City, New York, USA ¹¹ Shaare Zedek Medical Center, Jerusalem, Israel
51	O R	14:00 – 14:07	Introducing ECMO to a non-cardiac surgery centre: Can we eliminate the learning curve? Carlos Sanchez-Glanville; Mary Brindle; Steve Menzies; Tanya Spence; Jaime Blackwood; Tanya Drews; Steven Lopushinsky Alberta Children's Hospital, Calgary, Alberta, Canada
52	O R	14:12 – 14:19	Determinants of survival and resource utilization for ECMO in the United States, 1997-2009 Jun Tashiro ¹ ; Eduardo A. Perez ¹ ; David Lasko ² ; Juan E. Sola ¹ ¹ Division of Pediatric Surgery, DeWitt-Daughtry Family Department of Surgery, Leonard M. Miller School of Medicine, University of Miami, Miami, Florida, USA ² South Florida Pediatric Surgeons P.A., Plantation, Florida, USA
53	T R	14:24 – 14:31	Combined approach in the management of refractory chylous ascites in paediatric oncology patients Alkudayri A; Habib Z; Koussayer S Department of Surgery, King Faisal Hospital & Research, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia
54	O R	14:24 – 14:31	Trend analyses of retained surgical items in children in the United States, 1997-2009 Jun Tashiro ¹ ; Eduardo A. Perez ¹ ; David Lasko ² ; Juan E. Sola ¹ ¹ Division of Pediatric Surgery, DeWitt-Daughtry Family Department of Surgery, Leonard M. Miller School of Medicine, University of Miami, Miami, Florida, USA ² South Florida Pediatric Surgeons P.A., Plantation, Florida, USA

14:36 -15:00	Stretch Break and coffee
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15:00 - 16:30	Ethics session Moderator: Sarah Bouchard
	CAPS' Ethics Forum – Dr. Sarah Bouchard and CMPA

SATURDAY, SEPTEMBER 20

09:30 -10:30		Scientific Session # 7 Poster Podium Presentations Moderators: Sonia Butterworth & Sarah Bouchard	
55	P	09:30	Understanding childhood non-accidental trauma: Guidelines are needed for trauma surgeons and centers Y Ou; A Kroeker; J Riebe; A Randall; B Mohr; P Ehrlich CS Mott Children's Hospital, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA
56	P	09:34	Evaluation of a dedicated nurse practitioner/enterostomal therapist (Np/Et) role for children with Hirschsprung's disease (Hd) and anorectal malformations (Arm) Eveline Lapidus-Krol ¹ ; Kimberly Colapinto ¹ ; Karine Dupuis ¹ ; Jacob C Langer ^{1,2} ¹ Division of Pediatric General and Thoracic Surgery, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ² Department of Surgery, University of Toronto, Faculty of Medicine, Toronto, Ontario, Canada
57	P R	09:38	Rural vs urban treating trauma centers: Different mechanisms, similar outcomes Andrea M. Stroud ¹ ; Friedrich M. von Recklinghausen ² ; Daniel P. Croitoru ³ ¹ Dartmouth Institute for Health Policy & Clinical Practice, Lebanon, New Hampshire, USA ² Dartmouth Hitchcock Medical Center, Lebanon, New Hampshire, USA ³ Section of Pediatric Surgery, Department of Surgery, Geisel School of Medicine, Children's Hospital at Dartmouth, Dartmouth Hitchcock Medical Center, Lebanon, New Hampshire, USA
58	P R	09:42	Strategy to increase diagnostic yield of surgical lung biopsy in pediatric oncology patients Shannon N. Acker ¹ ; James T. Ross ¹ ; Megan K. Dishop ² ; Robin R. Deterding ³ ; David A. Partrick ¹ ¹ Department of Pediatric Surgery, Children's Hospital Colorado, Denver, Colorado, USA ² Department of Pediatric Pathology, Children's Hospital Colorado, Denver, Colorado, USA ³ Department of Pediatric Pulmonology, Children's Hospital Colorado, Denver, Colorado, USA
59	P R	09:46	Mortality rates associated with pediatric surgical conditions in low and middle-income countries in Africa: A call to action Michael H Livingston ^{1,2,3} ; Jennifer DCruz ¹ ; Julia Pemberton ¹ ; Doruk Ozgediz ⁴ ; Dan Poenaru ^{1,5} ¹ McMaster Pediatric Surgery Research Collaborative, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ² Clinician Investigator Program, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ³ Division of General Surgery, Western University, London, Ontario, Canada ⁴ Pediatric Surgery, Yale-New Haven Children's Hospital, New Haven, Connecticut, USA ⁵ Bethany Kids at Myung Sung Christian Medical Center, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia
60	P R	09:50	The burden of waiting: Dalys accrued from delayed access to pediatric surgery in Kenya and Canada Dan Poenaru ^{1,4} ; Julia Pemberton ^{1,2} ; Brian H Cameron ^{1,3} ¹ McMaster Pediatric Surgery Research Collaborative, Department of Surgery, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ² Department of Clinical Epidemiology and Biostatistics, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ³ McMaster Children's Hospital, Hamilton Health Sciences, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ⁴ BethanyKids at MyungSung Christian Medical Center, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia
61	P	09:54	Compliance with published guidelines for antibiotic use in the post-operative management of children with appendicitis Anna C. Shawyer ¹ ; Alexandra C. Hatchell ² ; Julia Pemberton ³ ; Helene Flageole ^{1,3} ¹ Division of Pediatric Surgery, McMaster Children's Hospital, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ² McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ³ McMaster Pediatric Surgery Research Collaborative, McMaster Children's Hospital,

			Hamilton, Ontario, Canada
62	P R	09:58	Neck and spine injuries in Canadian cheerleaders: An increasing trend Isabelle Hardy ¹ ; Steven R McFaul ² ; Dickens St Vil ¹ ¹ CHU Ste-Justine, Montreal, Quebec, Canada ² Public Health Agency of Canada
63	P	10:02	In-briefs: A novel patient resource for pediatric surgery nurse practitioners Julia Pond ¹ ; Taraneh Tofighi ² ; Julia Pemberton ² ; J Mark Walton ^{1,2} ¹ McMaster Children's Hospital, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ² McMaster Pediatric Surgery Research Collaborative (MPSRC), Department of Surgery, McMaster University Hamilton, Ontario, Canada
64	P	10:06	The level of evidence keeps improving: An updated analysis of the scientific program at the Canadian Association of Paediatric Surgeons annual meeting Flageole Helene ^{1,2} ; Kanters David M ¹ ; Tan Collin N ¹ ; Pemberton Julia ¹ ¹ McMaster Pediatric Surgery Research Collaborative, Department of Surgery, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada ² McMaster Children's Hospital, Hamilton Health Sciences, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada
65	P R	10:10	A systematic review and meta-analysis of gastrostomy insertion techniques in children Laura Baker; Alana Beres; Robert Baird McGill University, Division of Pediatric General and Thoracic Surgery, Montreal Children's Hospital, Montreal, Quebec, Canada
66	P	10:14	Design and sample size considerations for a randomised controlled trial comparing appendectomy and non-operative treatment of appendicitis in children Nigel J Hall ¹ ; Eveline Lapidus-Krol ¹ ; Justyna Wolinska ¹ ; Shawn St Peter ² ; Tom Jaksic ³ ; Alexis Arnaud ⁴ ; Tomas Wester ⁵ ; Jan Svensson ⁵ ; Ahmed Nasr ⁶ ; Erik Skarsgard ⁷ ; Risto Rintala ⁸ ; Daffyd Davies ⁹ ; Tim Jancelewicz ¹⁰ ; Richard Keijzer ¹¹ ; Mary Brindle ¹² ; Jan Goseman ¹³ ; Andreana Butter ¹⁴ ; Andrew Willan ¹⁵ ; Martin Offringa ¹⁵ ; Simon Eaton ¹⁶ ; Agostino Pierro ¹ ¹ Division of General and Thoracic Surgery, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ² Children's Mercy Hospital, Kansas City, Missouri, USA ³ Boston Children's Hospital, Boston, Massachusetts, USA ⁴ Centre hosp. régional et universitaire de Rennes, France ⁵ Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden ⁶ Children's Hospital of Eastern Ontario, Ottawa, Canada ⁷ Children's and Women's Hospital of British Columbia, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada ⁸ University of Helsinki, Finland ⁹ IWK Health Centre, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada ¹⁰ The University of Tennessee Health ScienceCenter, Memphis, Tennessee, USA ¹¹ University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada ¹² Alberta Children's Hospital, Calgary, Alberta, Canada ¹³ Hannover Medical School, Hannover, Germany ¹⁴ Children's Hospital of Western Ontario, London, Ontario, Canada ¹⁵ Child Health Evaluative Sciences, Hospital for Sick Children, Toronto, Ontario, Canada ¹⁶ Surgery Unit, UCL Institute of Child Health, London, United Kingdom
67	P R	10:18	Upper gastrointestinal contrast study may not be necessary for preoperative planning in children undergoing routine gastrostomy tube placement Paulette I. Abbas ^{1,2} ; Bindi J. Naik-Mathuria ^{1,2} ; Adesola C. Akinkuotu ^{1,2} ; Ashwin Pimpalwar ^{1,2} ¹ Texas Children's Hospital, Houston, Texas, USA ² Michael E. DeBaKey Department of Surgery, Baylor College of Medicine, Houston, Texas, USA

68	P	10:22	<p>Shit happens: Using integrated knowledge translation to address family knowledge needs of Hirschsprung's disease</p> <p>M. Morris ¹; K. Hobbs-Murison ^{1,2}; C. Holland ¹; E. Crawford ³; J. Elson ⁴; C. Beauchamp ⁴; B. Milne ⁴; K. Wittmeier ^{2,5}; R. Keijzer ^{1,2}</p> <p>¹Departments of Surgery and Pediatrics and Child Health, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada</p> <p>²Manitoba Institute of Child Health, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada</p> <p>³Swish Productions Ltd., Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada</p> <p>⁴Direct Focus Marketing Communications Inc., Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada</p> <p>⁵Centre for Healthcare Innovation SUPPORT Unit, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada</p>
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10:30 - 11:30	<p>JPS/Fred MacLeod Lecture</p> <p>Ronald B. Hirschl</p> <p>The Making of a Surgeon: 10,000 hours?</p>	
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12:00 - 14:00	<p>CAPS EDUCATIONAL SYMPOSIUM</p> <p>A Competency Based Education Model for Pediatric Surgery</p> <p>Moderator: Ted Gerstle</p>	
	<p>Presentations:</p> <p>Farhan Bhanji: "The Canadian Perspective"</p> <p>Ronald Hirschl: "The American Perspective"</p> <p>Juan Bass: "The RCPSC Pediatric Surgery Specialty Committee Perspective"</p> <p>Panel Discussion and Audience participation</p>	

14:00 - 14:10	President's Closing Remarks – Jacob Langer	
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18:30 – 24:00	Presidential Reception and Banquet	
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The RNA profile of nitrofen-induced hypoplastic lungs in congenital diaphragmatic hernia

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Background: To date, the mechanisms underlying nitrofen-induced lung hypoplasia in this rodent model of congenital diaphragmatic hernia are poorly understood. We aimed to identify differences between the entire transcriptomes of control and nitrofen-induced hypoplastic embryonic lungs.

Methods: We used a Next Generation Sequencing approach to profile changes in the expression of all RNA subclasses from fetal rat lungs isolated at embryonic day E13.5 following treatment of dams with nitrofen or vehicle olive oil at E9. A dataset of significantly different mRNA, miRNA, tRNA, rRNA, snRNA and snoRNA targets was generated. After normalization, selected mRNA-encoding genes found to be significantly different were identified through fold-change filtering and annotated for biological function and a subsample was validated using reverse transcriptase quantitative PCR.

Results: Nitrofen treatment induced 87 mRNA genes by more than 2 fold while 112 other genes were downregulated by at least 2 fold. mRNA gene expression was found to be organized into several clusters including extrinsic apoptotic signaling, thymic T cell selection, ventricular cardiac muscle tissue morphogenesis, water transport, sterol biosynthetic processes, iron transmembrane transporters, potassium ion transmembrane transport and also being involved in amphetamine treatment.

Conclusion: The obtained transcriptomes for control and nitrofen-induced hypoplastic lungs will help guide our future experiments to describe CDH-relevant miRNA evolutionary conservation between rats and humans and the expression correlation with their mRNA targets.

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